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The impact of geomagnetic storms on the development of headaches

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Abstract. This article examines the influence of geomagnetic activity — specifically geomagnetic storms — on human health, with a focus on the pathogenesis of headache syndromes. Clinical and epidemiological studies supporting the correlation between geomagnetic disturbances and the frequency or intensity of headaches are reviewed. Risk groups, associated symptoms, and preventive recommendations are outlined.

Keywords: geomagnetic storm, geomagnetic activity, headache, migraine, neurological symptoms, autonomic dysfunction.

Geomagnit bo'ronlarning bosh og'rig'ining rivojlanishiga ta'siri

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola geomagnit faollikning, xususan, geomagnit bo'ronlarning inson salomatligiga ta'sirini, bosh og'rig'i sindromlarining patogeneziga e'tiborni qaratadi. Geomagnit buzilishlar va bosh og'rig'ining chastotasi yoki intensivligi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni qo'llab-quvvatlovchi klinik va epidemiologik tadqiqotlar ko'rib chiqiladi. Xavf guruhlari, ular bilan bog'liq alomatlar va profilaktik tavsiyalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: geomagnit bo'ron, geomagnit faollik, bosh og'rig'i, migren, nevrologik alomatlar, vegetativ disfunktsiya.

Влияние геомагнитных бурь на развитие головных болей

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается влияние геомагнитной активности, в частности геомагнитных бурь, на здоровье человека с акцентом на патогенез синдромов головной боли. Рассмотрены клинические и эпидемиологические исследования, подтверждающие корреляцию между геомагнитными возмущениями и частотой или интенсивностью головных болей. Описаны группы риска, сопутствующие симптомы и профилактические рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: геомагнитная буря, геомагнитная активность, головная боль, мигрень, неврологические симптомы, вегетативная дисфункция.

Introduction

In recent years, increased solar activity and its consequences on Earth's magnetosphere — known as geomagnetic storms — have attracted significant attention in the healthcare field. These disturbances adversely affect the human body's electromagnetic balance, leading to a range of physiological disruptions, particularly in the nervous and cardiovascular systems.

Headache, especially migraine and tension-type headache, is among the most frequently reported symptoms associated with geomagnetic sensitivity. This article explores the link between geomagnetic phenomena and headache development, underlying pathophysiological mechanisms, and strategies to mitigate associated symptoms.

Physiological Effects of Geomagnetic Storms

Geomagnetic storms occur when high-energy particles ejected from solar flares penetrate the Earth's magnetosphere. These particles induce electrical currents and electromagnetic fields in the ionosphere, which may disrupt the homeostasis of the human nervous system.

Such electromagnetic fluctuations influence cerebral blood flow and autonomic regulation, potentially leading to cerebral hypoxia and vascular tone disturbances — both key factors in the development of headache syndromes. Individuals with preexisting neurological or cardiovascular conditions may experience an exacerbation of symptoms during geomagnetic disturbances.

Scientific Evidence and Research Findings

Multiple clinical and statistical studies have confirmed an increase in headache incidence during periods of heightened geomagnetic activity:

- A 10-year observational study conducted by the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences found that headache-related complaints rose by 20–30% during geomagnetic storms.

- Epidemiological studies in Japan and Germany recorded a 1.5–2-fold increase in migraine episodes on geomagnetically active days.

- A U.S. study (2018) reported a 17% rise in emergency department visits for headaches within 24 hours of geomagnetic disturbances.

- These findings suggest a robust correlation between solar-magnetic fluctuations and neurological symptomatology.

High-Risk Populations

Individuals most susceptible to geomagnetic influences include:

- Patients with neurocirculatory dystonia or autonomic dysfunction;
- Individuals with hypertension or hypotension;
- People with a history of **migraines** or chronic headaches;
- **Women**, particularly during the premenstrual phase;
- Elderly persons;
- Pregnant women and children.

These individuals often report accompanying symptoms such as dizziness, nausea, fatigue, palpitations, and insomnia during geomagnetic storms.

Prevention and Therapeutic Approaches

To minimize the adverse effects of geomagnetic storms on health, the following recommendations are advised:

- Reduce exposure to electromagnetic sources (e.g., limit use of electronic devices);
- Maintain a consistent sleep schedule and daily routine;
- Engage in stress-relieving activities: breathing exercises, meditation, walking;
- Follow a balanced diet, avoiding salty, fatty, and processed foods;
- Ensure adequate hydration (at least 1.5–2 liters of water per day);
- In cases of severe neurological symptoms, consult a physician for sedatives, vasoregulators, or analgesics.

Conclusion

Geomagnetic storms exert a significant impact on human health, especially on the central nervous and circulatory systems. These effects contribute to the onset or exacerbation of headache syndromes in sensitive individuals. Early identification of at-risk individuals and implementation of preventative strategies can help mitigate these adverse outcomes.

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